

THERMOMECHANICAL ANALYSES OF THIN COMPOSITE REFRACTORY LININGS

Alain Gasser ^{1,2}, Philippe Boisse ^{1,2}, Jacques Poirier ³, and Yves Dutheillet ⁴

¹ *Laboratoire de Mécanique des Systèmes et des Procédés, ENSAM, 151 bd de l'Hôpital, 75013 Paris, France*

² *ESEM, 8 rue Léonard de Vinci, 45072 Orléans Cedex 2, France*

³ *CRDM/Sollac, Rue du Comte Jean, 59240 Dunkerque, France*

⁴ *Electricité de France, EMA, Les Renardières, 77818 Moret-sur-Loing Cedex, France*

SUMMARY: Refractory linings protect steel structures from hot products they contain, like steel, aluminium or coal. Since steel and refractory materials have not the same thermal expansion, thermal stresses appear during thermal loading, inducing cracking. The aim of this study is to build a tool that help the design of such composite structures. Two models are developed. The first at the local scale is 3D and uses a smeared crack approach to describe the refractory behaviour. It allows to analyse structures that are not too complex (like steel ladles). The second can be used for more complex structures containing cooling tubes and/or anchors. A simplified element, a two-layered composite shell, is necessary for the finite element analyse. Its identification (with an inverse approach) and its validation are described. It is then applied to analyse the cracking in a part of a coal-fired power plant.

KEYWORDS: Refractory linings, layered shell element, inverse identification, thermomechanical analyses.

INTRODUCTION

Most structures containing very hot fluids have refractory ceramics to protect their metallic part which can not exceed a maximum value of temperature. The main application domains are the steel industry [1][2], the production of aluminium and electric energy [3].

The refractory ceramics are submitted to high thermomechanical loading due to temperature gradients (1650°C to 300°C in steel industry). Strains due to these temperature gradients and thermal expansion differences between refractory and metallic parts, can lead to damage in the refractory linings. In some cases, the industrial device has to be stopped. If the refractory lining design is based on an important experience of the involved industries (a strong mastery of corrosion phenomena), it is more and more promising to develop behaviour simulation methods of refactorised structures under thermomechanical loading.

The aim of this study is to develop finite element computing tools that will allow to bring a help for the design of refactorised structures like steel ladles (steel making industry) or coal-fired power plants (energy production). These linings are composite made of refractory castable (or bricks), and of a metallic envelop (casing), on which they can be anchored. The casing includes frequently tubes for the circulation of pressurised water. Expansion joints are present in the refractory. Three scales can be defined in this problem (Fig. 1): the first is the one of the components (tubes, anchors, expansion joints, ...) (local scale), the second is the one of the panel (meso-scale), and the third is the one of the structure (scale of the structure). To analyse a complete refactorised structure (several meters), it is not always possible to perform a 3D computation. Because of the complexity of the geometry, it is not possible to describe each detail like anchors, tubes or joints. The solution proposed in this work (Fig.1) is to use a structural equivalent finite element (in this study a two-layered shell element) that will described the whole thickness of the composite casing (refractory and metallic part). The objective of such an approach is to reduce the size of the finite element model and to render

possible the computations while describing the behaviour of the metallic casing and the damage of the refractory.

Fig. 1: 3D cell modelling (lining and casing with tubes) with an equivalent two-layered shell element allowing to analyse a complete structure.

STUDY AT THE LOCAL SCALE

The first step is to build a model at the local scale that can be used to analyse some refractorised structures that are not too complex.

Model description

The local scale is the one of the components (tubes, anchors, expansion joints, ...). The studied structures are made with steel and castable. The steel has an elastic-plastic behaviour and the castable behaviour is assumed elasto-plastic in compression and elastic-damageable in tension with softening [4][5] after the elastic part (Fig. 2a) using a smeared crack model [6]. Several types of smeared crack models are existing:

- fixed crack model [7]: the crack is initiated perpendicular to the maximum tensile principal stress in mode I, and its orientation is maintained fixed for a more important loading,
- rotating crack model [8]: the crack is also initiated perpendicular to the maximum tensile principal stress in mode I, but the crack direction can rotate to remain perpendicular to the maximum principal tensile stress,
- the multiple fixed crack model [9][10][11] is like to the fixed crack model, but secondary cracks can appear perpendicular to the existing cracks.

Here, it is a multiple fixed crack model that is used.

The softening part of the tension curve (Fig. 2a) is assumed, for simplification, to be a straight line with slope a . In 3D, the cracking is detected with the surface shown in Fig. 2b.

Since it is difficult to perform accurate tension tests on castable, the tension behaviour (Young modulus E , stress of first cracking σ_R , slope of softening a) is identified using a four point bending test [12] linked to an inverse method [13][14]. Indeed, a bending test is a structural test with tension and compression. So, a direct identification is not possible.

Fig. 2: (a) Uniaxial tension/compression behaviour; (b) shape of the crack detection surface (drawn in 2D).

Validation

A four point bending test was performed on a large plate (1.2m long) with some metallic tubes and an anchored refractory (Fig. 3a). The simulation of this test (Fig. 4) is compared to the experimental results. The cracks appear at the top of the tubes (Fig. 3b and 4a), and the load/displacement curves are in good agreement (Fig. 4b).

Fig. 3: Bending test on a panel (casing and refractory lining): (a) test, (b) cracking at the top of the tubes.

Fig. 4: 3D simulation of a bending test on a panel (casing and refractory lining): (a) damage in a half of a panel, (b) comparison between tests and simulation for the load/displacement curve.

Example of 3D analyse

The 3D model presented above can be used to analyse some structures that are not too complex, such as some steel ladles [15] (that have no anchors and no cooling tubes). Fig. 5a shows the quarter of the mesh of such a steel ladle. It contains two layers of refractory linings: a safety layer (made with castable) and a wear layer (made with bricks). The thermal cycle, linked to the filling and emptying of the steel at 1650°C , induces important stresses that damage the "cold" face of the safety layer (Fig. 5b).

Fig. 5: (a) Mesh of the quarter of a steel ladle; (b) damaged zones in the refractory lining ("cold" face of the safety layer).

MODELLING AT THE MESO-SCALE

Two-layered composite shell

In other cases, the structure is too complex to use a 3D modelling. The proposed solution is to define a simplified element built at the meso-scale (Fig. 1). The exterior layer (side of the casing) has an elastic-orthotropic behaviour, the second is elastic-damageable in order to describe the anchored refractory lining (Fig. 6). The behaviour of this element must be equivalent to the set of casing, anchors and lining. The shell parameters identification is performed using tension, bending, shear and thermal tests, on a representative cell containing several anchors (Fig. 7). The results of these tests are compared to the simulations obtained with the shell model. That allows, using an inverse approach [13][14], to identify the shell parameters. Since these tests are difficult to perform experimentally, they were simulated with the 3D model defined at the local scale (the one of the components) [16][17] and presented above.

Fig. 6: Composition of the two-layered composite shell.

Fig. 7: Tests used for identification and validation of the mechanical parameters of the composite shell.

Validation

This previous approach is validated using a test that was not used for the parameter identification: a panel under pressure load (Fig. 7). The comparison of the displacements (Fig. 8) between the 3D simulation and the two-layered shell simulation shows a good agreement. But the difference of computing time is important: the 3D model has 20000 degrees of freedom, and the shell model only 700.

Fig. 8: Panel under pressure (one quarter of the structure, fixed edges): comparison of displacements for 3D (a) and shell (b) analyses.

Example of a structure analyse

The two-layered shell element is then used to analyse a complete structure, for instance a cyclone (part of a coal-fired power plant, Fig. 9a). The damage in the refractory layer due to thermal loading of this cyclone is shown Fig. 9b. This damage is important because we did not take into account the expansion joints that allow to decrease the stresses. So, it is necessary to introduce them in the model.

Fig. 9: (a) Part of a coal-fired power plant (cyclone); (b) Analysis of the cyclone using two-layered shell elements (damage in the refractory layer).

Expansion joints

To take into account the expansion joints, the same approach can be used, but the 3D results are obtained using refactorised panels containing two perpendicular joints (Fig. 10a). The simulation of a tension/compression test of such a panel shows that the stress/strain curve presents two slopes (Fig. 10b). The first (E_t) is linked to open joints, the second (E_c) to closed joints. A solution is then to take twice more mechanical parameters for the two-layered composite shell: one set of parameters is related to open joints, the second to closed joints.

Fig. 10: (a) Representative elementary volume with two perpendicular expansion joints; (b) tension/compression behaviour of this volume.

CONCLUSION

To compute a refactorised structure containing thousand of anchors and tubes with as finite element method, it is necessary to use a simplified element. The proposed element is a composite shell with two layers. The thermal and mechanical parameters are identified using an inverse approach related to several 3D tests. Since they are difficult to performed experimentally, the results are obtained numerically, using a 3D model developed at the local scale. This approach is validated with a four point bending test on a real refactorised panel. The 3D model at the local scale allows to compute the cracking in the castable of a steel ladle, and the composite shell element allows to analyse more complex structures like a cyclone. This last analyse showed that it is necessary to take into account the expansion joints that are present in the refractory linings to decrease the thermal stresses. To take them into account in the shell element, twice more parameters are needed.

The presented approach is a tool that allows to estimate the damage in refactorised structures submitted to thermomechanical loading, and then to bring a help for the design of such structures to limit cracking.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors acknowledge the support provided by Electricité de France and Sollac/Usinor companies.

REFERENCES

1. Poirier, J., "Recent tendencies in refractories in relation with service in the steel industry", *Proceedings of 39th Colloquium on Refractories*, 1996, Aachen (Germany).
2. Peruzzi, S., Poirier, J., Glandus, J. C. and Huger, M., "Numerical study of the in-service behaviour of refractory parts used in continuous casting", *Proceedings of 6th ECERS Conference*, 1999, Brighton (UK).
3. Gordon, E. D., "Refractories in CFB applications", *Proceedings of 12th International Conference on Fluidized Bed Combustions*, 1993, San Diego (USA).
4. Petersson, P. E., "Crack growth developpement of fracture zones in plain concrete and similar materials", Report TVBM-1006 Div. Bldg. Mats., 1985.
5. Cotterell, B. and Mai, Y. W., "Fracture mechanics of cementitious materials", Blackie Academic & Professional, 1996.
6. Weihe, S., Kröplin, B. and de Borst, R., "Classification of smeared crack models based on material and structural properties", *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, 1998, Vol. 35, No. 12.
7. Rashid, Y. R., "Ultimate strength analysis of prestressed concrete pressure vessels", *Nuclear Engineering and Design*, 1968, Vol. 7.
8. Cope, R. J., Rao, P. V., Clark, L. A. and Norris, P., "Modelling of reinforced concrete behaviour for finite element analyses of bridge slabs", *Numerical Methods for Nonlinear Problems I*, Taylor et al., Eds., 1980.
9. Litton, R. W., "A contribution to the analysis of concrete structures under cyclic loading", *PhD Thesis*, University of California, 1976.
10. De Borst, R. and Nauta, P., "Non-Orthogonal Cracks in a Smeared Finite Element Model", *Eng. Comp.*, 1985, Vol. 2.
11. Hibbit, Karlsson and Sorensen, "Theoretical Manual of Abaqus Code", HKS Inc., 1997.
12. Lemaistre, H., "Etude des propriétés thermomécaniques de divers réfractaires", *PhD Thesis*, INSA de Lyon (France), 1998.
13. Marquardt, D. W., "An algorithm for least squares estimation of nonlinear parameters", *J. Soc. Indus. Appl. Math.*, 1963, Vol. 11, No. 2.
14. Schnur, D. S. and Zabaraz, N., "An inverse method for determining elastic material properties and a material interface", *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering*, 1992, Vol. 33.
15. Derré, V., Gasser, A. and Boisse, P., "Poche à acier de 270 tonnes à tenue améliorée", Report ESEM/Usinor, Orléans (France), 2000.
16. Andrieux, C., Gabis, V., Gasser, A., Boisse, P. and Rezakhanlou, R., "Castable anchoring optimization to improve service life of refractory linings", *Proceedings of UNITECR'97*, 1997, New Orleans (USA).
17. Boisse, P., Gasser, A., Poirier, J. and Rousseau, J., "Simulations of thermomechanical behaviour of composite refractory linings", *Composites Part B Engineering*, 2001 (to appear).